

Supporting Information for “Entangled States Induced by Electron-Phonon Interaction in Two Dimensional Materials”

José D. Mella,^{1,2} Hernán L. Calvo,³ and Luis E. F. Foa Torres¹

¹*Departamento de Física, Facultad de Ciencias Físicas y Matemáticas, Universidad de Chile, 8370448, Santiago, Chile*

²*School of Engineering and Sciences, Universidad Adolfo Ibáñez, 7941169, Santiago, Chile*

³*Instituto de Física Enrique Gaviola (CONICET) and FaMAF, Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, 5000 Córdoba, Argentina*

In this Supporting Information we provide a derivation of the phonon modes, a brief discussion on the electron–phonon induced gap, additional calculations for the local density of states, and more details about the calculations for the interferometric setup. Within the Supporting Information references are numbered as, e.g., equation S.1 and Figure S1, whereas regular numbers, e.g., equation 1 and Figure 1, refer to the main article.

PHONON MODES IN HONEYCOMB LATTICES

The bulk phonon dispersion shown in Figure 1a of the main text for a honeycomb lattice can be calculated by solving the eigenvalue problem:

$$D(\mathbf{G})\delta_{\mathbf{G}} = \omega_{\mathbf{G}}^2\delta_{\mathbf{G}}, \quad (\text{S.1})$$

where $D(\mathbf{G})$ is the dynamical matrix and $\delta_{\mathbf{G}} = (\sqrt{m_A}\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^A, \sqrt{m_B}\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^B)$ with $\mathbf{u}_{\mathbf{G}}^\alpha$ the phonon polarization vector and m_α the mass in sublattice $\alpha = \{A, B\}$. Considering elastic coupling between first nearest neighbor sites and in-plane modes, the elements of the dynamical matrix can be written as

$$D_{\alpha,\beta}(\mathbf{G}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m_\alpha m_\beta}} \sum_j \mathcal{R}(\theta_j) \mathbf{K} \mathcal{R}(-\theta_j) e^{i\mathbf{G}\cdot\mathbf{R}_{\alpha,\beta}} \quad (\text{S.2})$$

where the sum runs over the first nearest neighbors and $\mathbf{R}_{\alpha,\beta} = \mathbf{R}_\beta - \mathbf{R}_\alpha$ is the relative position between neighbor unit cells. The force constant matrix is defined along the x -axis as $\mathbf{K} = \text{diag}(\phi_L, \phi_T)$, where ϕ_L (ϕ_T) represents the longitudinal (transverse) elastic constant. The $\mathcal{R}(\theta_j)$ matrices correspond to a rotation in an angle θ_j formed by $\mathbf{R}_{\alpha,\beta}$ and the x -axis. The position of the two sites are $\mathbf{r}_A = (0, 0)$ and $\mathbf{r}_B = a_0(\sqrt{3}/2, 1/2)$, with a_0 the nearest neighbor equilibrium distance. The lattice vectors are $\mathbf{a}_1 = \sqrt{3}a_0(1/2, \sqrt{3}/2)$ and $\mathbf{a}_2 = \sqrt{3}a_0(-1/2, \sqrt{3}/2)$. The electron–phonon system is calculated by considering the high-energy phonon modes \mathbf{u}^\pm at the valleys $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{K}^\pm = \pm(\mathbf{b}_1 - \mathbf{b}_2)/3$, respectively, with \mathbf{b}_i the primitive vectors of the reciprocal lattice. Considering the following basis for the phonon eigenvectors:

$$\mathbf{R}_A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1, i, 0, 0)^T, \quad \mathbf{L}_A = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(1, -i, 0, 0)^T, \quad (\text{S.3})$$

$$\mathbf{R}_B = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0, 0, 1, i)^T, \quad \mathbf{L}_B = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(0, 0, 1, -i)^T, \quad (\text{S.4})$$

the valley phonon modes are $\mathbf{u}^+ = \mathbf{L}_A + \mathbf{R}_B$ at \mathbf{K}^+ and $\mathbf{u}^- = \mathbf{R}_A + \mathbf{L}_B$ at \mathbf{K}^- .

ELECTRONIC BULK BAND GAP

In Figure S1 we show the electronic band gap at \mathbf{K}^- when the inversion symmetry is broken. We compare the results

of the tight-binding model and the analytical gap around \mathbf{K}^- valley given by $3\sqrt{2}\gamma_1|\mathbf{L}_A^\dagger\mathbf{u}_A + \mathbf{R}_B^\dagger\mathbf{u}_B|$.¹ To break inversion symmetry, we change the mass on sublattice B. The high-energy phonon mode used in this work can be written as $\mathbf{u}^+ = \kappa_1\mathbf{L}_A + \kappa_2\mathbf{R}_B$, where κ_1 and κ_2 are such that when inversion symmetry is preserved, $\mathbf{u}^+ = \mathbf{L}_A + \mathbf{R}_B$. The electronic band gap can be seen in Figure S1 and is maximum when $\Delta m = m_B - m_A = 0$, i.e., when the system preserves inversion symmetry, and decreases when the latter is broken. Although not shown, the electronic band gap at \mathbf{K}^+ , produced by the time-reversal partner mode \mathbf{u}^- , presents a similar behavior.

Figure S1. Electronic band gap obtained by the tight-binding model and the analytical approximation when inversion symmetry is broken. The band gap is maximum when the inversion symmetry is preserved, i.e., $\Delta m/m_A = 0$. Parameters: $\gamma_1 = 0.01\gamma_0$, $\hbar\omega = 0.5\gamma_0$, $\Delta = 0.001\gamma_0$, $\phi_L = 1$ and $\phi_T = 0.25$.

LDOS IN GRAPHENE UNDER DIFFERENT ELECTRON–PHONON COUPLING AMPLITUDES

In Figure S2 we evaluate the local density of states ρ in the vicinity of the edge for a semi-infinite zigzag slab and using a typical value of graphene’s phonon frequency around the valleys ($\hbar\omega = 125$ meV). Panels (a) to (c) display different

Figure S2. Local density of states ρ for graphene shown on the logarithmic scale $\log(1 + \rho)$ for different values of the electron–phonon coupling. The phonon frequency used here is $\hbar\omega = 125$ meV. We use the following values for the electron–phonon coupling strength: $\gamma_1 = 0.002 \gamma_0$ (a), $\gamma_1 = 0.001 \gamma_0$ (b) and $\gamma_1 = 0.0002 \gamma_0$ (c). The blue zones depict the electronic band gap provided by the low energy approximation.

values of the electron–phonon interaction strength. We can see there that the electron–phonon interaction induced gap is of about $\Delta\varepsilon \simeq 8.5 \gamma_1$, in agreement with the low-energy estimation of ref 1, see blue zones in the figure. In panel (a) we use $\gamma_1 = 2 \times 10^{-3} \gamma_0 = 5.4$ meV, so the gap is $\Delta\varepsilon \simeq 46$ meV, while in panels (b) and (c) we reduce this coupling by a factor of 2 and 10, such that the induced gaps are $\Delta\varepsilon \simeq 23$ meV and 4.6 meV, respectively. In all cases the counterpropagating edge states bridging the gap are clearly visible. As in Figure 2 of the main text, the calculation of ρ includes phonon replicas up to second order, i.e., (n_1, n_2) with $n_1 + n_2 \leq 2$.

INTERFEROMETRIC SETUP

The selected configuration is a hexagon, as shown in Figure 3b of the main text, with alternating zigzag and Klein edges on each side of the polygon. This configuration allows for the wavefront to transit to the opposite side with minimal backscattering. An external magnetic field perpendicular to the plane is incorporated through Peierls substitution, which modifies the hopping amplitudes as

$$\gamma_{n,m} \rightarrow \gamma_{n,m} \exp \left[\frac{ie}{\hbar} \int_{r_m}^{r_n} \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot d\mathbf{r} \right], \quad (\text{S.5})$$

where we use the gauge $\mathbf{A}(x) = Bx\hat{e}_y$. A correct interpretation of the interference and Aharonov-Bohm oscillations requires a large device to avoid quantum Hall effect (QHE) and the width of the interferometer arms needs to be sufficiently large to avoid hybridization between opposing edges. This allows for the tracking of changes in the interference pattern and the Aharonov-Bohm oscillations in the conductance as the Fermi energy is varied. In our simulations, the transmission coefficients are calculated for a sample with and without electron–phonon interaction, connected to ideal leads.

Figure S3. Fourier transform of the transmission coefficients of Figures 3d and 3e of the main text for $\varepsilon = 0.5 \hbar\omega$ (a) and $\varepsilon = 1.1 \hbar\omega$ (b), respectively.

Another way to demonstrate interference in the *which path* interferometer under an external magnetic field is by analyzing the Fourier transform of the oscillation. In Figure S3 we calculate the Fourier transform of the transmission coefficients shown in Figure 3d and 3e of the main text. Aharonov-Bohm oscillations and their higher harmonics are clearly visible away from the bulk band gap in the Fourier transform of Figure S3b. Despite the electron–phonon coupling, all peaks in both systems coincide, suggesting a similar interference pattern. These patterns are usually observed in other graphene devices.^{2,3} When we consider the electron–phonon coupling, important differences appear for energies on the bulk gap (Figure S3a). Although there are peaks at the same location, their amplitudes differ. This peak is associated with the backscattering that occurs at the corners of the hexagonal device, which changes the valley polarization and phonon

mode, thereby allowing for interference. However, this effect is small compared with the system without electron–phonon coupling.

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